

பாண்டியன் கோவில் கலைகள் தமிழ் ஆய்விதழ்

அறிஞர்களால் மதிப்பீடு செய்யப்படும் ஆய்விதழ்

Pandian Tamil Journal of Temple Studies

A Peer-Reviewed Journal

Volume 4, SPL Issue 1, January 2024

E-ISSN: 2583-0880

The Pilgrimage to Vraj as a Pilgrim's Progress

K. Abilasha, Assistant Professor of English, Sri S. Ramasamy Naidu Memorial College,
Sattur, Tamil Nadu, India.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5257-9892>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10588504

Abstract

Vaishnavite sect believes Sri Narayana is God and there are numerous forms of Lord Vishnu. It even encountered Advaita philosophy with Dvaita and Vishishtadvaita by strongly upholding the supremacy and omnipotence of Sri Krishna. There are scriptures, philosophical texts, devotional poems, paintings, sculptures, art, cuisine dedicated to the Vaishnavite sect and references. They are widely revered in day to day life of Indians irrespective of their caste, religion or beliefs. With such a strong scripture, literature and philosophy with a huge following, there are hardly any areas left to explore. Yet, this paper proposes to discuss the pilgrimage to Vraj Bhoomi and state that it is a pilgrimage of a pilgrim who evokes the inward awakening of the unconditional love for Sri Krishna. During Raasleela Sri Krishna dances with every Gopi, a higher form of blessing where they get their own Krishna. Pilgrimage to Vraj Bhoomi is a journey to invite one's own Krishna to their heart through pure devotion and unconditional love. Sri Krishna chooses to visit the hut of Vidhura ignoring the luxurious palace of Duryodhana. He embraces poor Kusela, valuing his friendship. During Vana Bhojana Leela, he shares his food with cowherd boys though he is of noble birth. A devotee is expected to find the will to leave material love and develop spiritual unconditional love in the course of the devotional journey. Such a pilgrimage are the ones to Vraj where two divya desam Mathura and Thiru Aaipadi are located that give strong will and kindle the devotional spirit of the pilgrim.

Keywords: Pilgrimage, Vraj Bhoomi, Mathura, Thiru Aaipadi.

Introduction

Rabindranath Tagore beautifully expresses the magnanimous, generous and merciful heart of Sri Krishna that could be touched only by true devotion. Luxuries and loudness of the material world can never reach the blissful abode of God but a fumbling call of a devotee will reach God in nanoseconds. Tagore writes,

When I try to bow to thee, my obeisance cannot reach down to the depth where thy feet rest among the poorest, and lowliest, and lost.

Pride can never approach to where thou walkest in the clothes of the humble among the poorest, and lowliest, and lost. (Gitanjali 10)

For any Vaishnavite, this fact is proven through the stories of great devotees like Draupati, Dhuruva, Prahlada, Kusela, Vidhura etc., and it humbles the devotee and helps to stay away from material attractions. If there is a place that could make a devotee's heart melt like butter out of pure love for God, it is undoubtedly Vraj Bhoomi which includes two divya desam; Mathura and Thiru Aaipadi out of the 108 divyadesams. The divine abode of Sri Krishna is undoubtedly Vraj Boomi which comprises Mathura, Gokulam, Vrindavan, Govardhan, Barsana etc. Sri Krishna was born there and did all the Leelas and spent his

happy years with Gopis blessing them with his playful presence. This paper is a descriptive study that focuses on Vraj Bhoomi and includes the two Divyadesams. This paper purports to discuss the pilgrimage to Vraj Bhoomi from a spiritual context. Poet Narasinh Mehta lists the qualities of a Vaishnavite, a devotee of Lord Vishnu in his famous bhajan 'Vaishnava Janato' and confirms that the pilgrimage a Vaishnavite should go is not outside but within;

**One who gives up attachments
whose mind renounces**

**The name of Raam on his lips
whose pilgrimage is within. (L. 13-16)**

By keeping Tagore and Narsingh Mehta's lines as standard, this paper attempts a pilgrimage to the holiest abode of Sri Krishna, Vraj Bhoomi.

Vraj Bhoomi

Mathura is the birthplace of Sri Krishna. It is an Indian city located on the banks of the river Yamuna. Krishna Janmasthan temple is the Divyadesam in Mathura. As per Srimad Bhagavadam, Sri Krishna was born in a prison. Devaki and Vasudeva are imprisoned by Devaki's brother Kamsa after he learns that he will be killed by the eighth child of his sister Devaki. Kamsa imprisons the couple and kills all seven children of them. When Sri Krishna was born the eighth miracle happened leading to the safe transport of the baby by Vasudeva to the palace of Nandagopa and Yasodha making them foster parents of the baby. The two Divyadesam chosen for the study have been blessed by the very presence of Sri Krishna on the very first day of his birth and the best of his devotees, the Gopis. Sri Andal says in *Tiruppavai*

**The elusive son of blooming North Mathura;
Riverman *de facto* of grand Yamuna pure;
Appear'd in Ayar tribe a glow lamp and
Brought sanctity to mother's womb;... (Pasuram 5)**

Sri Krishna Janmasthan temple complex today is shared between a mosque and temple due to many historical political invasions over the years. The temple has a prison-like structure where Devaki gave birth to Sri Krishna and a shrine to depict Kamsa's killing of the baby girl Lokamaya by thrashing her on a wall. An ardent devotee of Sri Krishna feels Krishna in anything and everything. To a devotee the world is made of Krishna instead of atoms as Bharathiyar says, "And if I keep my finger inside a raging fire/ I only feel that sweet sensation of touching you." S/he believes all living and non-living entities are Krishna. Janmasthan, a busy temple fills a devotee with the joy of baby Krishna's birth and devotees can be seen offering, eating and distributing milk sweets. Vraj Bhoomi has innumerable varieties of delicacies made of milk, butter, curd, paneer and ghee. As Sri Krishna himself was a cowherd boy, devotees feast on the sweets sold and the sellers greet buyers with the greeting 'Radhe! Radhe!' A novice traveller would find it surprising as they would expect 'Krishna! Krishna!'. But Vrindavan and Vraj are considered the land of Radha's divine love.

As the temple is considered a sensitive place, the security checks are high and the devotees have too many restrictions in carrying their offerings. The temple campus is surrounded by numerous shops that sell baby Krishna idols, dolls, customised dresses, accessories for idols, devotional CD shops and shops selling pictures of Sri Krishna and Gopis. The place gives a festival mood as it signifies the birth of Sri Krishna. There is a pond, 'Pavithra Kund' next to the temple complex which is believed to be the place where they first

bathed baby Krishna. A pilgrimage to this place by devotees is done more as a spiritual inward journey as many devotees worship Sri Krishna in a mother-son relationship.

Thiru Aaipadi or Gokul is the palace of Nanda Gopa and Yasodha, the king and queen of Yadhavas. It is located 6-8 kilometres from Mathura. There are 2-3 places that claim to be the exact place where the Leela took place. As per the holy scriptures, the period of Sri Krishna dates back to 5000 years. There could be many natural geographical changes in the course of river Yamuna and buildings might have been destroyed. Hence this paper relies more on the inward journey a devotee feels on setting foot on Vraj than the temples. Sri Krishna spent his first 3.5 years in this palace where all Gopis showered him with love like a mother. They could not restrain themselves from getting attracted to this all-attractive baby in pitch black complexion aptly named Krishna. The palace today has the deities of baby Krishna. There are statues depicting Leela of baby Krishna like the killing of demoness Putana, bull demon Arishtasura etc. Nandhagopa and his people shift to Vrindavan after encountering many threats to the life of baby Krishna.

As mentioned earlier, Mathura temple was a prison and Thiru Aaipadi was a palace. Hence the temples lack the grandeur of SriRangam and other places. But that is the specific reason behind choosing these two Divyadesam and Vraj Bhoomi as a whole for exploration. Each of the Divyadesam has a miracle or an incident from holy Vaishnavite scriptures attached to it. But Mathura and Thiru Aaipadi have a whole lot of Sri Krishna's childhood mischiefs and miracles. Every street has a story and memory. There are many hearsay beliefs. One such belief is tamarind trees will not bear fruit in Vrindavan as Radha slipped by stepping on it. Apart from Mathura and Thiru Aaipadi, Vrindavan has Banke Bihari Temple, Shri Ranganatha Temple, Iskcon Temple, Prem Mandir and a whole lot of temples that belong to different Vaishnavite sects and another set of places like Raman Reti, Nidhi Van, Kalinga Ghat, Barsana and Govardhan. A physical pilgrimage to Vrindavan requires a minimum of 15-20 days excluding travel time. Each temple gives a unique vibration.

Banke Bihari temple is a place of divine bliss in a frenzy where devotees enthusiastically chant 'Radhe, Radhe' and dance. Devotees fondly offer sweets bought on the way to the temple to Banke Bihari ji who playfully accepts it. The environment is electric and it is a must-go temple during Holi. Prem Mandir Garden is an extravaganza on Earth where functional real-time dolls depict various leela of Sri Krishna. The deities are divine and the temple is a marvel. Shri Ranganatha temple is a Tamilnadu-style temple where the worship is done as it is done in Tamilnadu. Iskcon temple Vrindavan is one of the most visited temples where devotees chant and dance.

Nidhi Van is a sacred forest in Vrindavan where it is believed to date that Sri Krishna and Radha are performing Rasleela every night. No one is allowed to visit after sunset and it is believed that even animals, birds and insects are not there on the campus. Even the shrubs there are bent and unique. Every night the bed is made, sweets are offered and doors are closed. The next morning signs show that everything is used. A devotee's heart is the Nidhi Van. It should be always ready to host the Rasleela of Radha and Sri Krishna. Keeping it free from material things and filling it with devotion is a challenging pilgrimage inward. It requires total surrender and love. Devotees who worship Sri Krishna and consider themselves as Radha will find this place spiritually awakening. Raman Reti is a beautiful place where devotees roll, jump, pay obeisance and dance in the sand as it is believed that Sri Krishna played with Radha here. It is also believed that Sri Krishna played with his brother Balarama

here. So devotees jump and dance in frenzy and roll on the sand where once Sri Krishna det his foot. It is a normal sight for anyone who visits Vrindavan to see devotees taking a pinch of dust from a temple or ghat and placing it on their heads.

Kalinga Ghat near the banks of Yamuna is the place where Sri Krishna danced on the heads of the snake Kalinga, Chandra Sarovar where Brahma Vimohana Leela happened showing his omnipotence, Brahmanda Ghat is also the place where Sri Krishna ate clay and showed universe in his mouth, the place where Sri Krishna took rest with Sun and other planets after Kalinga Nartana Leela are some of the important places. Devotees go to two parikrama in Vraj; Vrindavan parikrama and Govardhan parikrama. While doing so one can witness some devotees lay down and pay homage called Ashtanga Namaskara on parikrama roads. Those are people who do parikrama not by walking but by ashtanga Namaskara. Some devotees will do 108 Ashtanga Namaskara in a place. In this method, they would even take 8-10 years to complete the parikrama. Vrindavan parikrama covers the whole of Vrindavan and Govardhan parikrama is walking around the Govardhan hill. Some devotees perform Vrindavan parikrama every day. Vrindavan is a holy place where anything and everything is right when it comes to loving Sri Krishna.

Radha's father is Vrishabhanu and his palace is in Barsana. This is a place where Radha is celebrated. The place echoes 'Radhe, Radhe' and the Holi celebration in Barsana is divine. A pilgrimage is complete when there is a transformation in the pilgrim. The physical efforts play a role in sculpting the mind. Moreover, the holy places bring in a spiritual transformation. Prem Sarovar in Barsana is a beautiful tank constructed in Rajasthan style. It is believed that this water is created by the tears and sweat of Radha and Sri Krishna. Boundless love created a fear of separation in Radha even though she was sitting on Sri Krishna's lap. This beautiful place is where Sri Krishna combed Radha's hair. A devotee develops love for God and develops this fear of separation from God out of love and not out of fear of punishment. It is unlikely for any Vaishnavite to compare themselves to Radha who is the divine incarnation of Lakshmi. Yet the deep desire of a Vaishnavite is to love Sri Krishna as much as the gopi if not Radha. This pilgrimage ends with Akrura ghat, the place Sri Krishna visited last in Vrindavan when he left with Akrura. It is believed that Sri Krishna bid farewell to Gopi here and left while they were crying and pleading with him to stay. He was around eleven years old then. This is the only place in Vrindavan where a gloomy sad feeling settles on. One could see devotees crying in the temple assuming themselves as gopi.

Conclusion

Indeed, this paper has given a brief view of the pilgrimage to Vraj Bhoomi highlighting a few places in specific. However, the places that could melt a devotee are discussed and the spiritual awakening it kindles is also discussed. The progress in a pilgrimage is not the external journey or the number of temples one visits but the advanced level of love one feels for God in the soul. To achieve that love for Lord Krishna, Vraj is the place one should go to get the spiritual quest transformed into a spiritual realization in the heart.

References

- [1] "Vaishnav Jan to Tene Kahiye Je - Lyrics and Translation." English Translation, www.shivpreetsingh.com www.shivpreetsingh.com/2018/12/vaishnav-jan-to-tene-kahiye-je-lyrics.html Accessed on 25.11.2023

Pandian Tamil Journal of Temple Studies

A Peer-Reviewed Journal

Volume 4, SPL Issue 1, January 2024

E-ISSN: 2583-0880

- [2] Tagore, Rabindranath. *Gitanjali*. Macmillan, *Internet Archive*, 1913. ia902608.us.archive.org/26/items/gitanjalisonoff00tagouoft/gitanjalisonoff00tagouoft.pdf Accessed on 25.11.2023
- [3] "Sri Andal- A Brief Life-Sketch." www.tiruppavai.net/about_andal.html Accessed on 25.11.2023
- [4] Navamohana Krishna Temple. (2023, October 13). In *Wikipedia*. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Navamohana_Krishna_Temple Accessed on 25.11.2023
- [5] "Maha Kavi Bharathiyar." *Vedanta Shastras Library*, <https://www.shastras.com/carnatic-music-krithis/maha-kavi-bharathiyar/> Accessed on 25.11.2023

Author Contribution Statement: NIL

Author Acknowledgement: Nil

Author Declaration: I declare that there is no competing interest in the content and authorship of this scholarly work.

The content of the article is licensed under [Creative Commons Attribution4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) International License.